

Marine Organisms as Source of Anticancer Agents: A Review

Goel Kirti¹, Kumar Ashish¹, Singh Randhir¹, Saini Vipin²

¹M.M College of Pharmacy, M.M (deemed to be) University, Mullana, Ambala, Haryana

²M.M University, Solan, Himachal Pradesh

Received: 9th Dec, 17; Revised: 30th Jan, 18, Accepted: 6th Feb, 18; Available Online: 25th Feb, 2018

ABSTRACT

Oceans cover more than 70% of the earth surface and the marine environment is highly diverse. Marine floras are taxonomically diverse, largely productive, biologically active and chemically unique offering a great scope for discovery of new anticancer drugs. The marine floras are rich in medicinally potent chemicals predominantly belonging to polyphenols and sulphated polysaccharides. The various active anticancer agents are derived from plants and terrestrial microorganisms and the isolation of C-nucleosides from the Caribbean sponge, Cryptothecacrypta, four decades ago, provided the basis for the synthesis of cytarabine that is the first marine derived anticancer agent to be developed for clinical use. Gemcitabine, one of its fluorinated derivatives that has also been approved for use in patients with pancreatic, breast, bladder, and non-small-cell lung cancer. ET-743, Aplidin R and Kahalalide F, has shown to show a positive therapeutic index and activity in resistant solid tumors that supports the ongoing clinical phase II/III trials. ET-743 represents as the first active agent against tumors developed in the past 25 years and has demonstrated a therapeutic potential in pretreated ovarian cancer. In recent times, a 44-member Dilactone macrolide swinholide J, epoxide of swinholide A, a known cytotoxic compound that was reported from the Red Sea sponge *Theonellas winhoei* and their cytotoxic properties indicated this compound to be less potent against oral carcinoma cell lines. This review revolves around the latest examinations and affirmations the colossal force of marine life frame as anticancer biomolecule sources

Keywords: Sponges, Bacteria, Fungi, Cytotoxicity, Bryostatsins, Aplidine

INTRODUCTION

Cancer, it is a highly dreadful human disease which is increasing with changing life style. Cancer treatments do not have much efficacious medicine, as the currently available drugs are causing side effects in some cases. In this context, the natural products obtained from medicinal plants has attained significance in the treatment of cancer and according to the WHO about 80% of the world's population primarily those of developing countries rely on plant-based medicines for the health care system¹. Natural products and their derivatives represent more than 50% of all the drugs in clinical use of the world and most of higher plants contribute not less than 25% of the total. Among all the anticancer drugs approximately 60% are of natural origin. Fruits and vegetables are the principal sources of vitamins (C, B, E), carotenoids, and fibers, and these contribute towards the apparent cancer-protective effects of the foods. An increase in dietary intake of natural antioxidants results in reduced coronary heart diseases, cancer mortality, as well as longevity^{2,3}. As we go back few decades, there has been a lot of interest among researchers in exploring of new herbal used drugs. This process has opened up new ways to produce significantly a diverse range of over 1,39,000 natural products, containing medicinally useful alkaloids, terpenoid derivatives, glycosides, steroids, polyphenolics and many more to the list. As per data from The National Cancer Institute (NCI) of the United States of America (USA), researchers have

screened about 1,14,000 extracts from an approximately 35,000 plant samples against a number of tumor systems⁴. Of the 92 anti-cancer drugs commercially available prior to 1983 in the USA and approved world-wide between 1983 and 1994, approximately 62% can be related to natural origin⁵. Some examples include vinblastine and vincristine (*Catharanthus roseus*), paclitaxel (*Taxusbaccata*, *T. brevifolia*, *T. canadensis*), camptothecin (*Camptothecaacuminata*), homoharringtonine (*Cephalotaxusharringtonia* var. *drupacea*), elliptinium (*Bleekeriavitensis*), epipodophyllotoxin, an isomer of podophyllotoxin (*Podophyllumpeltatum* roots), flavopiridol (*Dysoxylumbineectariferum*), and ipomeanol (*Ipomoea batatas*). The two medicinal products, paclitaxel and camptothecin were estimated to have nearly one third of the global anticancer market, respectively in the year 2002⁶. Numerous types of bioactive compounds have been isolated from plant sources. The utilization of herbal drug formulations in the management and treatment of cancer is emerging since the last thirty years. Moreover, the focus on natural sources for potential chemotherapeutic agents is still underway. Many of them are currently undergoing clinical trials or preclinical trials or under further investigation.

Among the natural drugs, the drugs from the marine sources are still in the infancy state despite of 95% of the

Table 1: Cytotoxic agents developed from natural sources⁷

Herbal Moeity	Anti-cancer use	Herbal Source
Etoposide	Testicular tumors, small-cell lung cancer	Podophyllumpeltatum, Podophyllumemodi
Cytarabine	Leukemia and non- Hodgkin lymphomas	Cryptothecacrypta
Vinblastine	Hodgkin's disease, non-Hodgkin, lymphoma, germ-cell tumors, Kaposi's sarcoma and breast cancer	Catharanthus roseus
Vincristine	Acute leukemia, Hodgkin's disease, non Hodgkins Lymphoma	Catharanthusroseus
Gemcitabine	Pancreatic, bladder, breast and non-small-cell lung cancer	Cryptothecacrypta
Vinorelbine	Activity in breast and non-Small cell and lung cancer	Catharanthusroseus

biosphere belongs to oceans. Recently, significant efforts have been made, by both pharmaceutical organizations and scholarly foundations, to segregate and distinguish new marine-determined particularly from faunal species. Regarding advancement and biodiversity, the ocean gives off an impression of being better than the earthly environment. As marine species contain around a half of the aggregate biodiversity, they are putting forth a tremendous source from which helpful therapeutics can be found. Over the previous decade, marine life forms have been perceived as an undiscovered asset for novel bioactive mixes. Marine verdures have been utilized for restorative purposes in India, China, the Near East and Europe, since old time. Chinese pharmacopeia suggests ocean growth based formulas for various physiological issues, for example, torment, abscesses, menstrual troubles and disease.⁸ Marine inferred biomolecules, for example, peptides, catalysts, chemical inhibitors, lipids has potential for the counteractive action and treatment for tumor growth. Refined peptides from these sources have been appeared to effectively affect a few human malignancies, for example, pancreatic, bosom, bladder and lung tumor.

Marine Floras Sources for Anticancer Agents

Bacteria and cyanobacteria

Marine microorganisms are a rich wellspring of new qualities, exploration of which prompt the revelation of new medications and remedial methodologies. The auxiliary metabolites created by marine microscopic organisms yielded numerous pharmaceutical items like novel mitigating specialists (e.g., Seudopterosins, Topsentins, Scytonemin and Manoalide), anticancer operators (e.g., Bryostatins, Discodermolide, Eleutherobin and Sarcodictyin) and anti-infection agents (e.g., Marinone). Hostile to Parasitic compound Valinomycin is acquired from *Streptomyces* sp. strains of Mediterranean Sea.¹¹

Bryostatin, specifically obtained from the Bryozoan, *Bugula neritina*, although some of types have been leached out from sponges and tunicates. Sorbicillin-derived alkaloids sorbicillactone A and its 2', 3'-dihydro analog sorbicillactone-B has indicated activity against leukemia cells free from any imperative cytotoxicity. Sorbicillactone-B has been derived from a salt-water culture of a bacterial strain *Penicillium chrysogenum* which has been derived from a sponge *Ircinia fasciculata*, a Mediterranean sponge species.¹²

Table 2: Therapeutically significant bio-molecules from marine organisms^{9, 10}

Organism	Agent	Bioactivity
Bacteria	Valinomycin	Anti-Parasitic
Cyanobacteria	Calothrixin A and B	Antimalarial
Cyanobacteria	Curacao extracts	Anti-proliferative
Fungi	Cephalosporin	Antibiotic
Fungi	Atherosclerosis	Antioxidants
Soft coral	Methanol extracts	Anticancer
Sponge	Kuanoniamines	Growth-inhibitors
Sponge	Steroid	Inflammation, asthma
Sponge	Ara-c	Antiviral
Cone snail	Conotoxins	Chronicpain

Cyanocobacteria

The cyanobacteria populace includes 150 genera and around 2000 types of extensive decent variety and the strength of marine cyanobacteria as anticancer specialists is most investigated among all marine determined chemicals. Other than cytotoxicity in tumor cell lines, a few mixes have risen as guide for the advancement of new anticancer medications e.g. cyanobacteria species incorporates *Nostoc*, *Calothrix*, *Lyngbya*, *Symposia* and so on.¹³

Fungi

Marine inferred growths give a lot of fundamentally and organically dynamic one of a kind optional metabolites in which Anthracenedione subordinates act like intense anticancer operators screened from the mangrove endophytic parasite *Halorosellinia* sp.. Moreover, *Guignardia* sp. for instance, Cytarabine, a hostile to leukemic medication and Trabectedin, a specialist for treating delicate tissue sarcoma that are created from growths sources. In addition, marine-determined parasites are additionally known to be a wellspring of against oxidative normal items, for example, Acremonin A from *Acremonium* sp. Xanthone subsidiary from *Wardomycesanomalus*. Cell reinforcements delay or anticipate oxidative harm and in this manner they might be valuable as therapeutics or nourishment added substances and distinctive kinds of Cephalosporin are confined from marine parasites which are utilized as anti-infection¹⁴.

Table 3: Some of the marine floral derivatives, peptides and their anticancer activities

Marine flora	Chemical agent	Biological activity
	Microbial flora	
Microcystisaeruginosa ^{23,24}	MicroviridinToxin BE-4, Siatoxin	Antibiotic, anticancer
Streptomyces peucetius ²⁵	Daunorubicin	Myeloid Leukemia and acute Leukemia
	Algal flora	
Nostocsporgiaforme ²⁶	Cryptophycin8	Greater therapeutic efficiency and lower toxicity than cryptophycin 14 in vivo
Cyanobacteria Nostoclinckia and Nostovsporgiaeforme ²⁷	Borophycin	Cytotoxicity against human epidermoid carcinomavartenu
Cyanobacteria ²⁸ Nostoclinckia ²⁹	Apratoxins Cyptophycin 1	Inhibit a variety of cancer cell lines Cytotoxicity-against human tumor cell and human solid tumors
Stylopodium sp. ³⁰ Chondria sp ³¹ Caulerpa sp. ^{32,33,34}	Stypoldione Condriamide A Caulerpenyne	Cytotoxic Cytotoxicity
Acanthophoraspicifera ^{35,36} Stigonema sp. ³⁷	Crude Scytonemin	Cytotoxicity, anticancer, anti-proliferating activity Tumoricidal activity on Ehrlich's ascites carcinoma Antiproliferative and Antinflammatoryactivities cells developed in mice
Leptolyngbya sp ^{38,39}	CoibamideA	Cytotoxicity against NCIH460 lung and mouseneuro 2a cell

Sponge

In excess of 10,000 sponges have been discovered worldwide and the greater part of them live in marine situations and marine sponges have yielded more than 70 novel mixes to date that show huge inhibitory movement towards a scope of protein kinases. A scope of bioactive mixes has been found in excess of 11 spoges genera. Three

of these genera (Haliclona, Petrosia and Discodemia) create compelling anticancer and calming specialists and these mixes have a wide range of organic exercises. Be that as it may, it's hard to disengage them in adequate amount for pharmacological testing¹⁵.

Table 4: Compounds with their chemistry and mechanism of action^(40, 41)

S.No.	Compound	Organism	Chemistry	Mechanism of action
1.	Aaptamine ^{42,43,44}	Sponge	Alkaloid	Induction of p21 and G2/M cell cycle arrest
2.	Cortistatin A ⁴⁵	Sponge	Alkaloid	Selective inhibition of angiogenesis
3.	Aplidine ⁴⁶⁻⁵³	Ascidian	Depsipeptide	Oxidation and inactivation of low molecular weight-protein tyrosine phosphatase activity
4.	Bastadine ⁶⁵⁴	Sponge	Alkaloid	Inhibition of angiogenesis in vitro and in vivo involves apoptosis
5.	Fucoxanthinol ⁵⁵	Ascidian	Carotenoid	Induction of apoptosis
6.	Lamellarin D ⁵⁶	Mollusk	Alkaloid	ErbB3 protein and PI3K- Akt pathway involved in necrosis induction
7.	Clavulone II ⁵⁷	Soft coral	Prostanoid	G1 cell cycle arrest and apoptosis
8.	Geodiamolides	Sponge	Peptide	Ineffectiveness of actin filaments
9.	Ircinin-1	Sponge	Sesterterpene	G1 phase inhibition and apoptosis induction
10.	Laxaphycins A and B	Bacterium	Cyclic peptides	Amplified polyploidy by putative topoisomerase II alterations
11.	Leptosins C and F	Fungus	Alkaloid	DNA topoisomerase I and II inhibition and apoptosis induction
12.	Onnamide A	Sponge	Polyketide	Protein synthesis inhibition
13.	Philinopside A	Sea cucumber	Saponin	Inhibition of angiogenesis and receptor tyrosine kinases

14.	Variolin B	Sponge	Alkaloid	Inhibition of cyclin-dependent and apoptosis induction kinases
15.	Aplidine ⁴⁶⁻⁵³	Ascidian	Depsipeptide	Induction of apoptosis with concomitant G1 arrest and G2 blockage
16.	Ascididemin	Ascidian	Alkaloid	Direct iminoquinone reduction and reactive oxygen species generation
17.	Cammbrescidin 800	Sponge	Alkaloid	Induction of erythroid differentiation and cell cycle arrest
18.	Dideoxypetrosynol A	Sponge	Fatty acid	Induction of apoptosis via mitochondrial signaling pathway
19.	Dolastatin 10 ⁵⁸⁻⁶⁴	Mollusk	Peptide	Binds to amino-terminal peptide of β tubulin containing cysteine
20.	Girolline	Sponge	Alkaloid	Induction of G2/M cell cycle arrest and p53 proteasome recruitment
21.	Halichondrin B	Sponge	Macrolide	Induction of mitotic blockage and derivative apoptosis
22.	Lissoclinolide	Ascidian	Fatty acid	G2/M cell cycle arrest
23.	Neoamphimedine	Sponge	Alkaloid	Induction of topoisomerase II α mediated catenation of DNA
24.	Psammaphin A	Sponge	Alkaloid	Inhibition of amino peptidase N and suppression of angiogenesis in vitro
25.	Alkylpyridinium	Sponge	Alkaloid	Induction of apoptosis and reduced cell adhesion
26.	Aeropylsinin	Sponge	Alkaloid	Induction of apoptosis on proliferating endothelial cells
27.	Bryostatin-1 ⁶⁵⁻⁷⁰	Bryozoan	Macrolide	Potential of ara-C induced apoptosis by PKC-dependent release of TNF- α
28.	Cephaiostatin	Worm	Steroid	Apoptosis and increased mitochondrial matrix density
29.	Chondropsin A	Sponge	Macrolide	In Vitro inhibition of V-ATPase enzyme
30.	Dehydrothryserol	Algae	Triterpene	Enhanced apoptosis induction in estrogen receptor negative breast cancer cells
31.	Diazonamide-A	Ascidian	Peptide	Disruption of mitosis and cellular microtubules with inhibition of GTP hydrolysis
32.	Dictyostatin	Sponge	Polyketides	Induction of tubulin polymerization
33.	Dolastatin 11 ⁷¹⁻⁷⁷	Mollusk	Peptide	F-actin stabilization by connection between two long-pitch strands
34.	Ecteinascidin- 743 ⁷⁸⁻⁸⁵	Ascidian	Isoquinoline	Telomere dysfunction increases susceptibility to ET-743
35.	GA3 polysaccharide	Alga	Polysaccharide	Inhibition of topoisomerase I and II
36.	Hemiasterlin	Sponge	Tripeptide	Induction of microtubule depolymerisation
37.	Kahalalide F ⁸⁶⁻⁹²	Mollusk	Depsipeptide	Potent cytotoxicity and induction of necrosis
38.	Lamellarin D	Mollusk	Alkaloid	Potent inhibition of topoisomerase I and II
39.	omega-3	fatty acids	Fish Fatty acid	--

Compounds Isolated from Sponges Jaspamide

It is a cyclic depsipeptide confined from sponges of the family Jaspis and Hemiastrella. It has a 15-carbon macrocyclic ring which contains three amino corrosive buildups. It has been demonstrated this is a bioactive compound initiating apoptosis in human promyelocytic leukemia cell line and T cells in mind tumor by Caspase-3 actuation and diminishing in Bcl-2 protein articulation.

Hemiasterlins are oligopeptides secluded from two unmistakable genera (Auletta; Siphonochalina) of wipe. There are three diverse Hemiasterlins with medicate improvement potential (Hemiasterlin, Hemiasterlin A, Hemiasterlin C) display cytotoxic and antitubulin movement. Mitotic restraint happens through authoritative to tubulin at the peptide locale in a way like Dolastatin¹⁶.
Discodermintetradecapeptides

These are another gathering of cytotoxic peptides got from sponges of the variety *Discodermia* sp. containing 13–14 referred to and uncommon amino acids as a chain, with a macrocyclic ring constituted by lactonization of a threonine unit with the carboxy terminal. Discodermins A–H is being tried against human lung cell line indicating cytotoxicity. Papuamides A–D are confined from sponges of the variety *Theonella*, are the main marine-determined peptides answered to restrain the disease of human T-lymphoblastoid cells by HIV-1 in vitro.^{17,18}

Mollusk

Mollusks are species that have an extensive variety of uses in pharmacology. Different sorts of straight, cyclic and conjugated peptides are found as restoratively intense anticancer biomolecules from the cone snail and other shelled creatures, for example, Kahalalides, Dolastatins, Ziconotide, Bursatellin, Keenamides etc.¹⁹

Anti-cancer Peptides from Marine Organisms

Today, more than 60% of the anticancer drugs commercially available are of natural origin. The relevance of the sea as a tool to discover novel anticancer compounds was validated by the discovery, development and marketing approval of isolated marine derived bioactive compounds. The available results clearly anticipated the potential of the marine ecosystem in cancer therapy²⁰. During the last decade about 2500 new metabolites with anti-proliferative activity have been reported. A recent review has discussed 68 new marine derived anticancer chemical entities, most of them with undetermined modes of action²¹. The identification of new targets for therapeutic intervention in cancer is instrumental to improve the physiological condition of cancer patients. The clinical results generated with a number of marine derived compounds such as the Dolastatins, Didemnin B, Aplidine have been recently reviewed. Most of the natural products of interest to the pharmaceutical industry are secondary metabolites, but there is a growing interest in products of primary metabolites such as various marine lipids, enzymes complex hetero polysaccharides and different types of peptides²². Although different types of anticancer bio-molecules are obtained from various types of marine organism this manuscript critically summarizes the developmental status of marine derived peptides from different micro and macro organism.

Beside these there are number of compounds obtained from marine as potential anti-cancer agents included in Table 4.1 and 4.2.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The above examples illustrate the intense excitement which surrounds the past decade's achievements in the area of new anticancer leads from marine organisms. The combination of novel structures and for some, novel mechanisms of action, is translating into new methods by which to treat cancer, and ultimately, improved outcomes, particularly for patients with solid tumors of the lung, breast, colon or prostate. The last decade has seen an ever evolving strategy for the screening and discovery of new anticancer leads from nature, and this is proving effective. Structures of compounds discussed in text,

including Ecteinascidin 743 (ET-743), a tetrahydroisoquinolone alkaloid currently in clinical trials for treatment of various cancers. Evaluation of crude extracts by in vivo screens to current evaluation of peak or pre fractionated libraries in mechanism-based assays, the level of sophistication and success has steadily improved. Screening strategies are continuing to evolve, probing new ideas and knowledge of cancer, introducing high throughput screening and new analytic methodologies. In part, the need for this continuing evolution has been stimulated by a desire to develop novel and less toxic therapies for cancer treatment. High throughput screening methods have both enabled more sophisticated mechanism based screening, and subsequently required the move to pre fractionation and peak library generation. These "prior-to-screening" purifications have the consequence of reducing the complexity of screening materials, increasing the titer of low abundance components, segregating nuisance substances into discrete fractions, and generally speeding up the time line from detection of a primary screening hit to identification of a molecular structure for the active substance. It can generally be concluded that contemporary screening protocols in natural products chemistry are using chromatographic purification steps, sometimes producing pure compounds, before biological or enzymatic bioassay. Coupled to these more effective paradigms for screening are new assays that evaluate natural products in more detailed, refined, and novel ways. For example, detailed knowledge of the cellular mechanisms controlling proliferation has yielded numerous targets for mechanism-based anticancer screens. A long-standing and perplexing question in marine natural products chemistry has been the identification of the metabolite producing organism or potentially metabolite bio transforming organism, in systems involving an invertebrate host and symbiotic microorganisms. This has been a surprisingly difficult issue to satisfactorily answer except in a very few cases, largely because of the difficulty of growing various microorganisms separately from their hosts. An alternative approach that has met with some success has been to isolate the various cell populations by centrifugation, sieving, or fluorescence-activated cell sorting, and then chemically analyze these samples for metabolites of interest. For example, in the case of the sponge *Dysidea herbacea* and its symbiotic cyanobacterium *Oscillatoria spongellae*, this has been accomplished on a couple of occasions and generally supports metabolic trends observed from working with pure strains of cyanobacteria. The cyanobacterial cells were found to contain a series of highly distinctive chlorinated peptides, previously isolated from work with the intact sponge, and which have strong structural precedence in metabolites isolated from the free-living cyanobacterium *Lyngbya majuscula*. Alternatively, a similar approach with the tunicate *Lissoclinum patella*, which harbors an abundance of the cyanobacterium *Prochloron* spp., yielded equivocal results for a series of distinctive cyclic peptides which were found to be associated with both the cyanobacterial and tunicate cells. In general, the approach of associating a specific

natural product with an isolated cell type is potentially flawed as it is conceivable, and even possibly expected with microbial populations, that metabolites will be secreted and become associated with cell types other than those responsible for their production. Hence, new approaches are needed which truly show the genetic and biochemical ability of a particular cell type to synthesize a metabolite of interest. A genetic approach has also been applied to this latter symbiosis which showed that *Prochloron* spp. do possess non ribosomal peptide synthetases.

REFERENCES

1. Gurib-Fakim, "Medicinal plants: traditions of yesterday and drugs of tomorrow," *Molecular Aspects of Medicine*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 1–93, 2006
2. Halliwell, "Dietary polyphenols: good, bad, or indifferent for your health?" *Cardiovascular Research*, vol. 73, no. 2, pp. 341–347, 2007.
3. D. O. Rios, L. M. G. Antunes, and M. D. L. P. Bianchi, "Bixin and lycopene modulation of free radical generation induced by cisplatin-DNA interaction," *Food Chemistry*, vol. 113, no. 4, pp. 1113–1118, 2009.
4. M. Cragg and M. R. Boyd, "Drug discovery and development at the National Cancer Institute: the role of natural products of plant origin," in *Medicinal Plant Resources of the Tropical Forest*, M. J. Balick, E. Elisabetsky, and S. A. Laird, Eds., pp. 101–136, Columbia University Press, New York, NY, USA, 1996.
5. J. G. M. Cragg, D. J. Newman, and K. M. Snader, "Natural products in drug discovery and development," *Journal of Natural Products*, vol. 60, no. 1, pp. 52–60, 1997.
6. N. H. Oberlies and D. J. Kroll, "Camptothecin and taxol: historic achievement in natural products research," *Journal of Natural Products*, vol. 67, no. 2, pp. 129–135, 2004.
7. H. Kikuzaki and N. Nakatani, "Antioxidant effects of some ginger constituents," *Journal of Food Science*, vol. 58, pp. 1407–1410, 1993.
8. B. K. Cart'e, "Biomedical potential of marine natural products," *BioScience*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 271–286, 1996
9. R. N. Lawrence, "Rediscovering natural product biodiversity," *Drug Discovery Today*, vol. 4, no. 10, pp. 449–451, 1999
10. B. S. Davidson, "New dimensions in natural products research: cultured marine microorganisms," *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 284–291, 1995
11. D. A. Devine and P. Marsh, "Prospects for the development of probiotics and prebiotics for oral applications," *Journal of Oral Microbiology*, vol. 1, pp. 1–11, 2009.
12. Bringmann G, Gulder TA, Lang G, Schmitt S, Stöhr R, Wiese J, et al. Large-scale biotechnological production of the antileukemic marine natural product sorbicillactone A. *Mar Drugs*. 2007;5:23–30
13. W. H. Gerwick, L. T. Tan, and N. Sitachitta, "Nitrogen containing metabolites from marine cyanobacteria," in *The Alkaloids*, G. Cordell, Ed., pp. 75–184, Academic Press, San Diego, Calif, USA, 2001
14. L. Lene, "Microbial metabolites-an infinite source of novel Chemistry," *Pure and Applied Chemistry*, vol. 68, pp. 745–748, 1996.
15. Zewails-Foote M, Hurley LH. Ecteinascidin 743: a minor groove alkylator that bends DNA toward the major groove. *J Med Chem* 1999; 42: 2493–97.
16. Gamble, W.R., Durso, N.A., Fuller, R.W., Westergaard, C.K., Johnson, T.R., Sackett, D.L., Hamel, E., Cardellina, J.H. 2nd, Boyd, M.R... 1999. Cytotoxic and tubulin-interactive hemiamsterlins from *Auleta* sp. and *Siphonochalina* spp. sponges. *Bioorg. Med. Chem.* 7:1611-1615.
17. Ford, P.W.; Gustafson, K.R.; McKee, T.C.; Shigematsu, N.; Maurizi, L.K.; Pannell, L.K.; Williams, D.E.; de Silva, E.P.; Lassota, P.; Allen, T.M.; et al. Papuamides A–D, HIV-inhibitory and cytotoxic depsipeptides from the sponges *Theonella mirabilis* and *Theonellaswinhoei* collected in Papua New Guinea. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 1999, 121, 5899–5909.
18. Aneiros, A.; Garateix, A. Bioactive peptides from marine sources: Pharmacological properties and isolation procedures. *J. Chromatogr. B Anal. Technol. Biomed. Life Sci.* 2004, 803, 41–53
19. Olivera, B.M. w-Conotoxin MVIIA: From Marine Snail Venom to Analgesic Drug. In *Drugs from the Sea*; Fusetani, N., Ed.; Karger: Basel, Switzerland, 2000; pp. 74–85.
20. Craigg, G.M.; Newman, D.J.; Weiss, R.B. Coral reefs, forests and thermal vents: The worldwide exploration of nature for novel antitumor agents. *Semin. Oncol.* 1997, 24, 156-163.
21. Mayer AMS, Gustaveson KR. Marine pharmacology in 2000: antitumor and cytotoxic compounds. *Int J Cancer.* 2003, 105, 291-299.
22. Amador M, Jimeno J., Paz Ares L., Cortés Funes H., Hidalgo M. Progress in the development and acquisition of anticancer agents from marine sources. *Ann Oncol.* 2003, 14(11): 1607-1615
23. A. R. Arment and W. W. Carmichael, "Evidence that microcystin is a thio-template product," *Journal of Phycology*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 591–597, 1996.
24. L. Shi, W.W. Carmichael, and P. J. Kennelly, "Cyanobacterial PPP family protein phosphatases possess multifunctional capabilities and are resistant to microcystin-LR," *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, vol. 274, no. 15, pp. 10039–10046, 1999.
25. H. Sakagami, M. Kashimata, M. Toguchi et al., "Radical modulation activity of lignins from a mangrove plant, *Ceriops decandra* (Griff.) Ding Hou," *In Vivo*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 327–332, 1998.
26. R. E. Moore, "Cyclic peptides and depsipeptides from cyanobacteria: a review," *Journal of Industrial Microbiology*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 134–143, 1996.
27. L. Lene, "Microbial metabolites-an infinite source of novel Chemistry," *Pure and Applied Chemistry*, vol. 68, pp. 745–748, 1996

28. G. A. Schiehser, J. D. White, G. Matsumoto, J. O. Pezzanite, and J. Clardy, "The structure of leptosphaerin," *Tetrahedron Letters*, vol. 27, no. 46, pp. 5587–5590, 1986.
29. R. Banker and S. Carmeli, "Tenuecyclamides A-D, cyclic hexapeptides from the cyanobacterium *Nostoc spongiaeforme* var. *tenua*," *Journal of Natural Products*, vol. 61, no. 10, pp. 1248–1251, 1998
30. H. Luesch, R. E. Moore, V. J. Paul, S. L. Mooberry, and T. H. Corbett, "Isolation of dolastatin 10 from the marine cyanobacterium *Symploca* species VP642 and total stereochemistry and biological evaluation of its analoguesymplostatin 1," *Journal of Natural Products*, vol. 64, no. 7, pp. 907–910, 2001.
31. W. H. Gerwick and W. Fenical, "Ichthyotoxic and cytotoxicmetabolites of the tropical brown alga *Styopodium zonale* (Lamouroux) papenfuss," *Journal of Organic Chemistry*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 22–27, 1981
32. J. A. Palermo, P. B. Flower, and A.M. Seldes, "Chondriamides A and B, new indolic metabolites from the red alga *Chondriasp*," *Tetrahedron Letters*, vol. 33, no. 22, pp. 3097–3100, 1992.
33. J. L. Fischel, R. Lemee, P. Formento et al., "Cell growth inhibitory effects of caulerpenyne, a sesquiterpenoid from the marine algae *Caulerpa Taxifolia*," *Anticancer Research*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 2155–2160, 1995.
34. D. Parent-Massin, V. Fournier, P. Amade et al., "Evaluation of the toxicological risk to humans of caulerpenyne using human hematopoietic progenitors, melanocytes, and keratinocytes in culture," *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health A*, vol. 47, no. 1, pp. 47–59, 1996.
35. P. Barbier, S. Guise, P. Huitorel et al., "Caulerpenyne from *Caulerpa taxifolia* has an antiproliferative activity on tumor cell line SK-N-SH and modifies the microtubule network," *Life Sciences*, vol. 70, no. 4, pp. 415–429, 2001.
36. H. R. Vasanthi, *Biomedical and pharmacological studies of somemarine algae of gulf of mannar south east coast of India*, Ph.D. thesis, 2002.
37. H. R. Vasanthi, G. V. Rajamanickam, and A. Saraswathy, "Tumoricidal effect of the red algae *Acanthophora spicifera* on Ehrlich's ascites carcinoma in mice Seaweed Res," *UtilNet*, pp. 217–224, 2004.
38. C. S. Stevenson, E. A. Capper, A. K. Roshak et al., "Scytonemin—a marine natural product inhibitor of kinases key in hyperproliferative inflammatory diseases," *Inflammation Research*, vol. 51, no. 2, pp. 112–114, 2002
39. R. A. Medina, D. E. Goeger, P. Hills et al., "Coibamide A, a potent antiproliferative cyclic depsipeptide from the Panamanian marine cyanobacterium *Leptolyngbya* sp.," *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, vol. 130, no. 20, pp. 6324–6325, 2008.
40. Mayer A and Gustafson KR. Marine pharmacology in 2002–2004: Anti-tumour and cytotoxic compounds. *Eur J Cancer*. 2006;42:2241–2270.
41. Mayer A and Gustafson K R. Marine pharmacology in 2005–2006: Anti-tumour and cytotoxic compounds. *Eur J Cancer*. 2008;44: 2257–2287.
42. Eferl R., Wagner E.F. Ap-1: A double-edged sword in tumorigenesis. *Nat. Rev. Cancer*. 2003;3:859–868. doi: 10.1038/nrc1209.
43. Gopalakrishnan A., Tony Kong A.N. Anticarcinogenesis by dietary phytochemicals: Cytoprotection by nrf2 in normal cells and cytotoxicity by modulation of transcription factors NF- κ B and ap-1 in abnormal cancer cells. *Food. Chem. Toxicol*. 2008;46:1257–1270. doi: 10.1016/j.fct.2007.09.082.
44. Kasibhatla S., Brunner T., Genestier L., Echeverri F., Mahboubi A., Green D.R. DNA damaging agents induce expression of fas ligand and subsequent apoptosis in t lymphocytes via the activation of NF- κ B and ap-1. *Mol. Cell*. 1998;1:543–551. doi: 10.1016/S1097-2765(00)80054-4.
45. Aoki S, Watanabe Y, Sanagawa M, Setiawan A, Kotoku N, Kobayashi M. Cortistatins A, B, C, and D, anti-angiogenic steroidal alkaloids, from the marine sponge *Corticium simplex*. *J Am Chem Soc*. 2006;128:3148–3149
46. Rinehart K.L., Gloer J.B., Cook J.C., Mizesak S.A., Scohill T.A., "Structures of the Didemnins, Antiviral and Cytotoxic Depsipeptides from a Caribbean Tunicate". *J Am Chem Soc.*, 1981, 103, 1857-1859.
47. Erba E., Bassano L., Di Liberti G., Muradore I., Chiorino G., Ubezio P., Vignati S., Codegoni A., Desiderio A., Faircloth G., Jimeno J., D'Incalci M. Cell Cycle phase perturbations and apoptosis in tumour cells induced by aplidine. *Br J Cancer*. 2002, 86:1510-17.
48. Broggin M, Marchini S., Borsott P., Galliera E., Erba E., Taraboletti G., Giavazzi R., Jimeno J., Faircloth G., D'Incalci M. Aplidine, a new anticancer agent of marine origin, inhibits vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) secretion and blocks VEGF-VEGFR-1 (flt-1) autocrine loop in human leukemia cells MOLT-4. *Leukemia*, 2003, 17, 52-9.
49. Anthony A., Paz-Ares L., Twelves C., Cortes-Funes H., Kaye S., Pronk L., Celli N., LopezLazaro L., Guzman C., Jimeno J. Phase I and Pharmacokinetic (PK) Study of APL (APL) Using a 24-Hour, Weekly Schedule. *Proc Am SocClinOncol*. 2000; abstract #734
50. Ciruelos E.M., Twelves C., Dominguez M.J., Mckay H., Anthony, A. Castellanos D., Bezares S., Ruiz A., Lopez-Lazaro L., Jimeno J., Celli C., Cortes-Funes H., Paz-Ares L. Phase I clinical and pharmacokinetic study of the marine compound APL (APL) administered as a 3 hour infusion every 2 weeks. *Proc Am SocClinOncol*. 2002, abstract # 422.
51. Bowman A., Izquierdo M.A., Jodrell D., Martinez M., Cicchella B., Jimeno J., Guzman C., GermaLluch J., Celli N., Smyth J. Phase I Clinical and Pharmacokinetic (PK) Study of the Marine Compound APL (APL), administered as a 1 Hour Weekly Infusion. *Proc Am SocClinOncol*. 2001, abstract #476.

52. Armand J.P., Ady-Vago N., Faivre S., Chieze S., Baudin E., Ribrag V., Lecot F., Iglesias L., López-Lázaro L., Guzmán C., Jimeno J., Ducreux M., Le Chevalier T., Raymond E. Phase I and Pharmacokinetic Study of APL Given as a 24-Hour Continuous Infusion Every Other Week (q2w) in Patients (pts) with Solid Tumor (ST) and Lymphoma (NHL). Proc Am Soc Clin Oncol. 2001, abstract #477
53. Maroun J.A., Goel R., Stewart D.J., Tomiak E., Belanger K., Soulieres D., Charpentier D., Seymour L., Matthews S., Jimeno J., Guzman C. Phase I Study of APL in a 5 Day Bolus Q 3 Weeks in Patients with Solid Tumors and Lymphomas. Proc Am Soc Clin Oncol 2001; abstract #2082.
54. Aoki S¹, Cho SH, Ono M, Kuwano T, Nakao S, Kuwano M, Nakagawa S, Gao JQ, Mayumi T, Shibuya M, Kobayashi M., Bastadin 6, a spongean brominated tyrosine derivative, inhibits tumor angiogenesis by inducing selective apoptosis to endothelial cells., *Anticancer Drugs*. 2006 Mar 17(3):269-78.
55. Kazuto takahashi, masashi hosokawa, hiroyuki kasajima, kazuteru hatanaka,³ kazuhiko kudo, norihiko shimoyama, and kazuo miyashita, anticancer effects of fucoxanthin and fucoxanthinol on colorectal cancer cell lines and colorectal cancer tissues, *Oncol Lett*. 2015 Sep; 10(3): 1463–1467.
56. Christian Bailly, Anticancer Properties of Lamellarins, *Mar Drugs*. 2015 Mar; 13(3): 1105–1123
57. Huang YC¹, Guh JH, Shen YC, Teng CM., Investigation of anticancer mechanism of clavulone II, a coral cyclopentenone prostaglandin analog, in human acute promyelocytic leukemia, *J Biomed Sci*. 2005;12(2):335-45.
58. Nuijen B, Bouma M, Manada C, et al. Pharmaceutical development of anticancer agents derived from marine sources. *Anticancer Drugs* 2000; 11: 793–811.
59. Sings HL, Rinehart KL. Compounds produced from potential tunicate-blue-green algal symbiosis. *J Ind Microbiol Biotechnol* 1996; 17:385–96.
60. Pitot HC, McElroy EA Jr, Reid JM, et al. Phase I trial of dolastatin-10 (NSC 376128) in patients with advanced solid tumors. *Clin Cancer Res* 1999; 5: 525–31.
61. Harrigan GG, Luesch H, Yoshida WY, et al. Symplostatin 1: a dolastatin 10 analogue from the marine cyanobacterium *Symploca hydroides*. *J Nat Prod* 1998; 61:1075–7.
62. Luesch H, Moore RE, Paul VJ, Mooberry SL, Corbett TH. Isolation of dolastatin 10 from the marine cyanobacterium *Symploca* species VP642 and total stereochemistry and biological evaluation of its analogue symplostatin 1. *J Nat Prod* 2001; 64:907–10.
63. Pettit GR, Kamano Y, Herald CL, et al. The isolation and structure of a remarkable marine animal antineoplastic constituent: dolastatin 10. *J Am Chem Soc* 1987;109: 6883–5.
64. Bai R, Pettit GR, Hamel E. Binding of dolastatin 10 to tubulin at a distinct site for peptide antimetabolic agents near the exchangeable nucleotide and Vinca alkaloid sites. *J Biol Chem* 1990;265: 17141–9.
65. Pettit GR. The bryostatins. *Fortschr Chem Org Naturst*. 1991;57:153-195.
66. Pagliaro L, Daliani D, Amato R, et al. Phase II trial of bryostatin-1 for patients with metastatic renal cell carcinoma. *Cancer*. 2000;89 :615-618.
67. Varterasian ML, Mohammad RM, Shurafa MS, et al. Phase II trial of bryostatin 1 in patients with relapsed low-grade nonHodgkin's lymphoma and chronic lymphocytic leukemia. *Clin Cancer Res*. 2000;6: 825-828.
68. Zonder JA, Shields AF, Zalupski M, et al. A phase II trial of bryostatin 1 in the treatment of metastatic colorectal cancer. *Clin Cancer Res*. 2001;7: 38-42.
69. Ahmad I, Al-Katib AM, Beck FW, et al. Sequential treatment of a resistant chronic lymphocytic leukemia patient with bryostatin 1 followed by 2-chlorodeoxyadenoside: case report. *Clin Cancer Res*. 2000; 6: 1328-1332.
70. Mayer A and Gustafson KR. Marine pharmacology in 2002–2004: Anti-tumour and cytotoxic compounds. *Eur J Cancer*. 2006; 42: 2241–2270.
71. Jordan A, Hadfield JA, Lawerence NJ, McGown AT. Tubulin as a target for anticancer drugs: agents which interact with the mitotic spindle. *Med Res Rev* 1998;18:259–96.
72. Bai R, Pettit GR, Hamel E. Dolastatin 10, a powerful cytostatic peptide derived from a marine animal. Inhibition of tubulin polymerization mediated through the Vinca alkaloid binding domain. *Biochem Pharmacol* 1992;43:2637–45.
73. Gerwick WH, Tan LT, Sitachitta N. Nitrogen-containing metabolites from marine cyanobacteria. In: Cordell G, editor. *The alkaloids*. San Diego: Academic Press; 2001. p. 75–184.
74. Cruz-Monserrate Z, Mullaney J, Harran P, Pettit GR, Hamel E. Dolastatin 15 binds in the Vinca domain of tubulin as demonstrated by hummel-dreyer chromatography. *Eur J Biochem* 2003;270:3822–8.
75. de Arruda M, Cocchiato CA, Nelson CM, et al. LU103793 (NSC D669356): a synthetic peptide that interacts with microtubules and inhibits mitosis. *Cancer Res* 1995; 55: 3085–92.
76. Villalona-Calero M, Baker S, Hammond LA, et al. Phase I and pharmacokinetic study of the water-soluble dolastatin 15 analog LU103793 in patients with advanced solid malignancies. *J Clin Oncol* 2001;19:857–69.
77. Vera M, Joullie MM. Natural products as probes of cell biology: 20 years of didemnin research. *Med Res Rev* 2002; 22:102–45.
78. Rinehart K.L., Holt T.G., Fregau N.L. Ecteinascidins 729, 743, 745, 759^a, 759^b and 770. Potent antitumor compounds from the Caribbean tunicate *Ecteinascidia Turbinata*. *J Org Chem*. 1990, 55(15), 4515-4516.
79. Jimeno J.M., Faircloth G., Cameron L. Cameron L., Vega E., Meely K., Rinehart K., Fernandez-Sousa, JM. Progress in the acquisition of new marine derived anticancer compounds: development of ecteinascidin-

- 743 (ET-743). *Drugs of the Future*. 1996, 21(11), 1155-1165.
80. Minuzzo M, Marchini S, Broggin M, Faircloth G, D'incalci M and Mantovani R: Interference of transcriptional activation by the anti-neoplastic drug ET-743. *Proc.Natl.Acad.Sci.USA*. 2000, 97: 6780-6784.
81. Jin S, Gorfajn B, Faircloth G and Scotto K: Ecteinascidin 743, a transcription-targeted chemotherapeutic that inhibits MDR1 activation. *Proc.Natl.Acad.Sci.USA*. 2000, 97, 6775-6779.
82. Friedman D, Hu Z, Kolb EA, Gorfajn B and Scotto KW: Ecteinascidin-743 inhibits activated but not constitutive transcription. *Cancer Res*. 2002, 62, 3377-3381.
83. Kanzaki A, Takebayashi Y, Ren XQ, Akiyama S., Bates S., Pommier Y.: Overcoming multidrug drug resistance in P-glycoprotein/MDR1-overexpressing cell lines by ecteinascidin 743. *Mol Cancer Ther*. 2002, 1, 1327-1334.
84. Damia G; Silvestri S; Carrassa L; Filiberti L; Faircloth G T; Liberi G; Foiani M; D'Incalci M: Unique pattern of ET-743 activity in different cellular systems with defined deficiencies in DNA-repair pathways. *Int J Cancer*. 2001, 92, 583-588.
85. Takebayashi Y; Pourquier P; Zimonjic D B; Nakayama K; Emmert S; Ueda T; Urasaki Y; Kanzaki A; Akiyama S I; Popescu N; Kraemer K H; Pommier Y: Antiproliferative activity of ecteinascidin 743 is dependent upon transcription-coupled nucleotide-excision repair. *Nat Med*. 2001, 7, 961-966.
86. Hamann MT, Otto CS, Scheuer PJ, "Kahalalides: Bioactive peptides from a marine mollusk *Elysia rufescens* and its algal diet *Bryopsis* sp.", *J. Org. Chem*, 1996, 61, 6594-660.
87. Hamann MT, Scheuer PJ, "Kahalalide F: A bioactive depsipeptide from the sacoglossan mollusk *Elysia rufescens* and the green alga *Bryopsis* sp.", *J Am Chem Soc*. 1993,115, 5825-5826.
88. Garcia-Rocha M, Bonay P, Avila J, "The antitumor compound Kahalalide F acts on cell lysosomes", *Cancer Lett*, 1996, 99, 43-50.
89. Suarez Y., Gonzalez L., Cuadrado A., Berciano M., Lafarga M., Muñoz A. Kahalalide F, a new marine derived compound induces oncosis in human prostate and breast cancer cells. *Mol. Cancer Therapeutics*, 2003, 863-872.
90. Supko J.G, Lu H., Jimeno J.M., Grant W., Faircloth G.T. "Preclinical pharmacology studies with the marine natural product Kahalalide F". AACR-NCI-EORTC International Conference on Molecular Targets and Cancer Therapeutics, November 16-19, 1999. Washington D.C. Abstract no. 315.
91. Ciruelos E., Trigo JM., Pardo B., Paz-Ares L., Estaun N., Cuadra C., Domínguez MJ., Marin A., Ruiz A., Jimeno J., Izquierdo MA. A phase I clinical and pharmacokinetic (PK) study with KahalalideF (KF) in patients (pts) with advanced solid tumours (AST) with a continuous weekly (W) 1-hour IV infusion schedule. 14th NCI-EORTC-AACR Congress, Frankfurt, Germany. *European Journal of Cancer*, 19-22 November 2002, Vol 38, Supplement 7, pp S33, Abstract 95.
92. Schellens J.H.M., Rademakerlakhai J.M., Horenblas S., Meinhardt W., Stokvis E., M.DeReijke T., Jimeno J., Lopez-Lazaro L., Lopez-Martin J.A., Beijnen J.H. Phase I and pharmacokinetic study of kahalalide F in patients with advanced androgen resistant prostate cancer ASCO 38th Annual Meeting. Orlando, Florida, May 18-21, 2002, Proc.113a, Vol., 21, Abstract 451.